

Encoding Medieval Charters in preparation for a Diplomatics Semantic Web

Combining the TEI with the *Vocabulaire International de Diplomatique*

Zarko Vujosevic, Georg Vogeler

Abstract

This contribution considers the problem of encoding concepts of diplomatics in digital scholarly editions. We follow the practice of annotation approach: using standard TEI (Text Encoding Initiative), enhancing it with concepts from the *Vocabulaire International de Diplomatique* (VID). Transferring this approach to the digital database *Diplomatarium Serbicum Digitale* (DSD), it becomes obvious that the VID could be improved. The SKOS version of it makes this possible. We discuss how simple reorganisation, addition of terms and only rare changes in the existing definitions allow to use the VID for specialisations of generic TEI elements and demonstrate this in an example. The effect of this approach is that a semantic web based model of charter descriptions can be extracted from TEI encoding.

Introduction

The paper is dedicated to Michael Gervers, one of the forerunners of Digital Diplomatics, on the occasion of the 50th anniversary of his D.E.E.D.S. Project founded in 1975 (Documents of Early England Data Set – [D.E.E.D.S Project | Department of Historical and Cultural Studies](#); Gervers 1978). Since then, Michael Gervers has continuously contributed that Digital Diplomatics moves on. The increased integration of digital representations of charters in portals portal like *Monasterium.net*¹ or *Diplomata Belgica*² is one major future perspective. Nevertheless, other paths have to be followed. In particular, the establishment of descriptive standards allows aggregation of data sets from different sources in and Linked Open Data environment, and the Web-of-Data activities of the W3C, also

¹ The portal www.monasterium.net, launched in 2002, is a virtual archive of European charters of the Middle Ages and Early Modern Age, currently containing more than 650.000 documents. Within archival fonds and research collections those are displayed in different levels of presentation (from “full package” with images, regest/abstract, transcription, diplomatic description and commentary with bibliography to a simple archival description accompanied by one or another photo).

² <https://www.diplomata-belgica.be> is the modernisation of an old initiative published on CD-ROM in 1997: Demonty 1997.

known as the Semantic Web, could help to create a kind of global database of charters.³

The path towards a descriptive standard has already began 17 years ago, when diplomatists suggested an XML schema for charters, the Charters Encoding Initiative (CEI; Vogeler 2004; 2005; 2006; 2010). Since then other standards have improved and in particular the Text Encoding Initiative (TEI) has become the major reference for many research questions in the humanities.⁴ It covers a good part of what diplomatists are interested in (Vogeler 2015; 2019). On that basis Sean Winslow has recently suggested extensions of the TEI to cover the needs of diplomatists (2018, 2019, 2020–2022).

This paper will discuss how this development and the web of data proposals by the W3C could be integrated to help diplomatists to publish full digital representations of charters, containing transcriptions, descriptions and commentaries, that can be reused by other scholars for different research questions. Nicolas Perreux has invested tremendous efforts creating an European corpus of charter texts (CEMA, Perreux 2020; Magnani/Perreux 2020). His work demonstrates the research possibilities of such a corpus, although it currently uses only plain text and basic descriptions of charters. Taking up the impulse by Michael Gervers, we will try to demonstrate how the integration of semantic web resources and XML encoding could foster digital diplomatics. To that end, needs and perspectives from the point of view of diplomatists will be discussed using the experience of the *Diplomatarium Serbicum Digitale*.⁵

An abstract model of diplomatics research interest

One core task of diplomatics research is the *discrimen veri ac falsi* (Kölzer 2010), i.e. the evaluation whether a charter is what it pretends to be. To achieve this, diplomatists use an interesting distinction between the (1) legal act, (2) historical information provided by a document, and (3) the document itself, the “written artefact” (Vogeler 2019). That means that one legal act could be (and mostly is) presented in more than one written artefact (original, copies, register entries, excerpts, transsumpts, forgeries...). Copies of documents (including “diplomatic” forgeries) can report a legal act correctly, although their diplomatic form is not original or they don’t carry any means of authentication. On the other hand, even a

³ <https://www.w3.org/standards/semanticweb/data> and <https://www.w3.org/2013/data/>. See Berners Lee et al. 2001 for the initial vision.

⁴ <https://tei-c.org>.

⁵ The idea of making a digital database of medieval charters and letters issued by Serbian auctors was developed at the Balkan Institute of the Serbian Academy of Sciences and Arts and has been realised as *Diplomatarium Serbicum Digitale* (DSD) in frames of the EU funded international project “Community as Opportunity: The creative archives’ and users’ network” (2015–2018). On DSD project history and its evolution stages see Vujosevic et al. (2014) and Vujosevic--Old Wine (2019).

“historical” forgery can contain correct information about historical reality, although the legal act described in the document has never happened. According to this, diplomatics editors consider charters usually in a mixture of their textual and their physical form, while archivists focus on the latter. Many diplomatics editors consider themselves as historians. Therefore, they additionally extract a core of historical information from charters and discuss their value as historical sources.

In a research tradition dominated by printed books, the oscillating combination of legal act, historical information, and the written artefact is not always easy to identify. Therefore, those different perceptions may not be clearly expressed, as classical research structures material through “numbers” or “diplomatic units”, merging various written artefacts of a single legal act into a single text (in the critical editions by the MGH, for instance). But even Michele Ansani, who has argued against a New Philology approach toward charter texts, acknowledges the ontological distinctions (2006). Digital diplomatics offers better solutions in this regard. It can go beyond the (digital) edition itself and use semantic web technologies for standardised representation and recognition of all facets of charters. Following the ideas of a pluralistic view on text proposed by Patrick Sahle (2013, 2016), different perceptions of the “diplomatic unit” can be unified in a multi-perspective model (Vogeler 2019), in which all of them reference each other, but none of them are necessary for the establishment of a “diplomatic unit”. That is particularly important as diplomatists and historians are dealing with all forms of a “diplomatic unit” even if some of them do not exist anymore: editions of charters in the tradition of the MGH contain “deperdita” i.e. descriptions of lost documents, they extrapolate on the palaeography of the model used for a forgery, and they also try to “reconstruct” texts (contents) of lost originals.⁶

Semantic Web technologies support this as they implement a graph representation of information. Graph databases offer a practical technology for this multi-perspective approach, as has been demonstrated by Andreas Kuczera (2016, 2020) or Colin Sippl and Manuel Burghardt (2023). They consist of pointers between conceptual entities: a written act points to a legal act (documenting it) and vice versa; an authentic copy points not only to the written original but also to the legal act; a physical forgery can point to a social reality although no legal act has happened. Witnesses authenticate a legal act even without a written act, while a seal authenticates any kind of physical objects, even if they don’t represent a legal act. The diplomatic unit is established by closing and clustering the network of these references. At the moment no formalism can be given for this. For instance: one could perceive the relationship in terms of FRBRoo⁷, which describes documents from a library perspective distinguishing between the intellectual creation (“work”), its verbal expression and the physical manifestations. In these terms, the legal act

⁶ Examples: *Merowinger 2* (2001) 489-495. on dealing with (the respective) deperdita; Koch (2018) 77-90 concerning the Privilegium minus/maius.

⁷ <http://www.cidoc-crm.org/frbroo>

would be considered a work, its textual representation an expression and the written document a manifestation singleton. However, this would leave the relationship between the physical means of authentication (e.g. a seal or a signature) and the legal act out of scope, and would describe the legal act only as an intellectual creation (“work”), but not as a social reality that changes the status (ownership, rank, ...) of real historical people. Another example would be the proposal by John Bradley and his colleagues (2019) to model charters as factoids focussing on their historical content. This helps to model the historical information provided by a charter, but neglects the physical and textual form, how charters convey this information, and the diplomatic considerations on the form.

Fortunately these theoretical modelling questions do not have to be decided. With the semantic web the W3C provides a technology to express the references as structured data and allows multiple proposals for vocabularies and ontologies. Under the open world assumption the clustered networks of references will manifest themselves, when, for instance, the *Abbildungsverzeichnis europäischer Herrscherurkunden* points to the archival identifiers and critical editions, the *Regesta Imperii* point to critical editions, *Monasterium.net* points to the *MGH* or the *RI*, historians create prosopographical databases pointing to critical editions or archival resources, like in the POMS and PASE projects (Bradley et al. 2019), etc. The semantic web is the standard to publish graph based data on the web and to interconnect it, and it is a good method to describe diplomatics’ multiperspectivity on charters, whatever concept (e.g. of a legal act or a written artefact) particular editions or projects do follow.

Therefore, the task to be solved is finding a way that brings the richness of Semantic Web based models of charters into the practice of XML encoding. The following will make a proposal on how this can be achieved.

XML

Charters and their diplomatic descriptions are texts, and the digital humanities have established XML encoding as the standard of digital representation of texts. XML, as embedded markup, supports the structural analysis of texts very well. For textual objects in general, the guidelines of the TEI have established themselves as the major standard. However, for the case of charters, there are no common standards used yet. Attempts like the proposal by Poulimenou et al. (2009) for an XML schema to describe charters were never used to publish data accessible to diplomatists. Other XML schemata like the CDLM proposal by Michele Ansani (2000-2020) or the XML used in the Cartago charter database (<http://www.cartago.nl/nl/wat-zit-erin/structuur>) remained project specific. Only the CEI has found a wider distribution: *RI*, *Monasterium.net*, the republication of the constitutiones of Charles IV by the

MGH working group at the Berlin-Brandenburgische Akademie der Wissenschaften⁸, some reuse in small collections (Ivanovs/Varfolomeyev 2017).

Compared to these domain specific standardisation attempts, the TEI is established as a de-facto standard of humanities work with texts, and in use for charters: the Anglo-Saxon charters prototype of the King's College, London,⁹ the projects in the Elec-portal of the Ecole des Chartes¹⁰, the Spanish CHARTA corpus (Isasi Martínez et al. 2014)¹¹, or the ACTÉPI project¹². As Vogeler (2015) has described, the TEI-P5 version covers a wide part of what diplomatists need. But still, it does not support the data exchange for diplomatists very well, as they have to create individual interpretations. For instance, the Spanish CHARTA project was not interested in features specific to medieval charters, but only in a solid transcription (Spence 2014), while Diple (Desenclos/Jolivet 2014) and the encoding of the Anglo-Saxon charters (Nelson et al. 2005-2018) use XML/TEI with individual typing of diplomatic structure. In order to offer further solutions within this concept, Sean Winslow (2018, 2019, 2020–2022)--himself a student of Michael Gervers--recently has suggested a standardised extension to the TEI.

This may not be satisfactory for data exchange. We would like to argue that the combination of semantic web representations of diplomatic knowledge and XML/TEI encoding could also serve diplomatists. TEI offers a good ground for the general description of manuscript documents and the text written on them. An extension of TEI with different features and concepts, specific for diplomatic research, is a long and incalculable process, and it is good that Sean Winslow has already started it with his proposal, suggesting controlled vocabularies to create a granular description of more generic diplomatics related elements, such as “diploPart” or “auth” (Winslow 2020–2022). For the time being, an alternative approach is using the basic nomenclature (i.e. elements) of the TEI as it is, specifying taxonomy and descriptions with the help of attributes.¹³ The ACTÉPI project is applying this system, being an example of quite successful use of TEI for diplomatic purposes.¹⁴ This approach can take a step further in order to facilitate data exchange and tool reuse. Instead of developing own attribute values (such as “analyse” or “contre-sceau”), we suggest using the already established system of diplomatic terminology: the *Vocabulaire International de la Diplomatie* (VID). We will exemplify this with the charters of the

⁸ <http://telota.bbaw.de/constitutiones/index.html>

⁹ <http://www.aschart.kcl.ac.uk/>

¹⁰ <http://elec.enc.sorbonne.fr/>

¹¹ <https://www.redcharta.es/>

¹² <https://actepi.hypotheses.org>, technically realised by the Pôle Document Numérique de la MRSH (Caen)

¹³ On TEI structure and rules of procedure: <https://www.tei-c.org/release/doc/tei-p5-doc/en/html/index.html>.

¹⁴

http://www.unicaen.fr/recherche/mrsh/sites/default/files/public/document_numerique/manuel_ecartae.pdf.

Serbian medieval rulers as they are recorded in the *Diplomatarium Serbicum Digitale* (DSD, see note 5 above). Therefore, we will first present a proposal how to modify the VID that it answers to general critique and--in particular--that it fits to the needs of encoding Serbian charters in the context of the above mentioned DSD project. We will then describe the TEI/XML encoding for some examples of the Serbian charters, making use of these modifications.

VID

Many of the concepts interesting to diplomatists and not available in the TEI are covered by a standardisation attempt of the Commission Internationale de la Diplomatie--the *Vocabulaire International de la Diplomatie* (Carcél Ortí 1997, 1. ed. 1994). This work can be used in a digital environment. Michele Ansani suggested already in 1999 using it as the starting point of a domain ontology (Ansani 1999). Since 2013, it has become part of the semantic web (Vogeler 2013; www.cei.lmu.de/VID), and Francisco Alvarez Carbajal suggested in 2015 a path to integrate the VID into TEI encoding (Alvarez Carbajal 2015).

However, the VID is not complete enough to be considered as the only authority for the common set of diplomatics knowledge. Already directly after publication, Bernard Barbiche (1995), Rolf Große (1996) and Olivier Guyotjeannin (1996) pointed out missing concepts or definitions falling behind the state of research.

The VID was created as a multilingual thesaurus, i.e. a list of terms in various languages. The terms are organised by headings in two levels. Some terms are organised in lists of subterms, and many include pointers to related terms. The terms and the headings can easily be converted into structures made available by the W3C SKOS vocabulary.¹⁵ This has been achieved in the online representation of the VID by automatic conversion (Vogeler 2013). The SKOS version has several advantages: For instance, the separation of names ("label") and abstract concept as well as the organisation of the logical concepts independently from the numbering scheme and the sequence in the text, e.g. avoiding the work-around of VID_196bis to insert the "arenga" at a specific position in the numbering sequence after having finalized the numbers.

Making use of these advantages, the SKOS version of the VID could be improved by manual curation keeping the existing formal definitions. For instance, VID/SKOS models the headings of the printed versions as concepts: the concept identified by http://www.cei.lmu.de/VID/#VID_TOC_15 ("Nature juridique des actes") is only a result of the headings in the printed VID. It is synonymous with the entry n. 424 <http://www.cei.lmu.de/VID/#424> in the VID. A `skos:exactMatch` declares this easily. The possibilities of SKOS to express hierarchies of concepts

¹⁵ On SKOS (Simple Knowledge Organization System) see <https://www.w3.org/2004/02/skos/> and Isaac / Summers 2009.

(`skos:broader`, `skos:narrower`) helps to integrate diplomatic phenomena currently missing in the VID as sub-terms without changing existing descriptions and numbers. Integrating further hierarchy into the VID allows searching for generic terms expanding automatically to the specialised terms.

In the following, we want to describe some proposals for modifications to the VID/SKOS by

1. restructuring the SKOS concepts
2. adding new concepts, and
3. conceptual modifications.

These modifications are based on diplomatic practice, in particular from the experience of the *Diplomatarium Serbicum Digitale*.

1. Restructuring the SKOS concepts

As the hierarchy of terms in the printed version of the VID was intended only as a guide to the reader and not a consistent system, some of the SKOS concepts can be organised in a better way. It is obvious that VID 182 (*cadre formel*) merges two concepts (protocol / eschatocol) in one entry. The translations suggested by the VID for no. 182 indicate this distinction already, but the current wording of the VID does not offer a simple definition of both terms as separate entities. As a result, the SKOS version of the VID has definitions for VID 182 and VID 182a which do not correctly correspond to the terms associated by `skos:prefLabel` with the concept. The resulting structure can keep VID 182 for the general concept of formal framing the charter text, but should make clear that there is an initial and concluding type of this. This applies even when some diplomatists use the term “protocol” for both, distinguishing the position by adding a specifier (“Eingangs- und Schlußprotokoll”). In fact, as SKOS uses abstract identifiers for the concepts, the definition of VID 182 can remain, though some of the labels assigned to VID 182 (*Eingangsprotokoll*, *protocolle initiale*) have to move to the new concepts defined as a narrower concept to VID 182 (VID_add_16).

VID 347 is another example of a merged concept, which could be reorganised. It is a narrower concept to VID 345 and includes variants by position (dorsal or marginal notes) as well as the functional distinctions between notes written in preparation and processing of the charter in the chancery (VID 180) and those added after engrossment and issuing, including VID 33. This distinction would suggest adding concepts for “notes dorsales” (VID_add_14) and “notes marginales” (VID_add_15) to make clear that they may also be functionally different.

In some cases, the logical hierarchy in the VID could be more specific. VID 53 (*Une copie*) is certainly a broader term for VID 54 to 64 (*copie authentique*, *informe*, *figurée* etc.), or even to VID 81. The same can be applied to VID 42 (*L'original*) and VID 43-51 (*originaux multiples*, *chirographe* etc.), VID 111 (*faux*) and VID 113-130 (*acte falsifié*, *altération matérielle*, etc.), VID 145 (*Les éléments figurés*) and VID

146-157 (*invocation figurée, chrismon etc.*), or VID 199 (*Les dispositions de l'acte*) and the clauses in VID 200-205, where VID 205 (*Une clause*) can be considered a broader concept to VID 206-244. VID 206 (*clauses de forme*) could further be considered a broader concept to VID 207-236, and, in fact, all entries from 184 to 264 are narrower terms to 183 (*Une formule*). Technically, this can be achieved by a simple change of the existing *skos:broader* statements. To avoid weakening existing relationships, the transitive versions *skos:broaderTransitive* and *skos:narrowerTransitive* allow the inference of the current relationships from the new.

VID 562 (*La date de temps*) and 563 (*La date de lieu*), as subterms of VID 561 (*La formule de date*), refer only to a textual phenomenon (“... est la formule qui ...”), leaving out the conceptual chronology of the legal act and production of the charter. Separating the historical date and place of issue from the *verbal description* of this date and place given in the document helps to handle cases, where diplomatists can infer a chronology and/or geographical place of issuing which is different from that written on the charter, or the indication of date/place of issue in the charter text is missing.¹⁶ We suggest using VID 562/563 for marking-up information given in the document and VID 560 as the generic term for the conceptual date. Adding concepts for the list of events mentioned in the definition of VID 560 could be a possible enhancement of VID.

Other structural modifications result from mis-assignments of terms in a specific language. VID 529 (“Un sceau d'emprunt”) defines two German terms which represent separate concepts: “Siegelbitte” is the act of asking for a seal by a person not being part of the legal transaction, “Siegelbittzeugen” describes the witnesses to this act.¹⁷ Adding them as concepts of their own (VID_529a and VID_529b) as related terms and adding “Fremdbesiedlung” as a German label to VID 529 improves the situation.

2. Adding new concepts

The experience with charters of different provenance, including Serbian, suggests to add further narrower concepts. Extensions in the SKOS version of the VID can easily be achieved: The missing **rescript** (Große 1996:237) can be added as a sub concept to VID_TOC_13 (“Nature diplomatique des actes”). Große (1996:237) also criticized the scope of the definition of “privilege” (VID 393) which should include royal and imperial charters as well. The simple declaration of an additional entry for a broader concept to both categories of issuers and declaring VID 394-395 to be

¹⁶ An example of inferring the date and place of issuing, which are missing in the charter text: Vujosevic (2005) 63-64.

¹⁷ Examples: https://www.monasterium.net/mom/DE-StABa/Langheim/1334_I_17/charter?q=Siegelbitt*
https://www.monasterium.net/mom/AT-StiAHe/DuernsteinCanReg/1378_I_07/charter?q=Siegelbitt*
https://www.monasterium.net/mom/DE-BayHStA/KUAlidersbach/00523.1/charter?q=Siegelbitt*

narrower concepts of VID 393 can solve this problem. Further additions of definitions for royal and imperial privileges as sub-concepts to the generic “privilege” would then balance the general scope. The same is true for the observation of Olivier Guyotjeannin (1996) that the concept of **Kurzarenga** (an arenga integrated into the dispositio) is missing: it can easily be inserted into the logics of the SKOS version of the VID as sub-concept to VID 196bis (VID_add_28). Große’s (1996:237) and Guyotjeannin’s (1996) suggestions to extend the coverage for German royal charters in general and for French royal charters in the 14th century in particular fit into this strategy. However, this can only be achieved by a thorough review of the according literature which cannot be done in this paper.

Adding new concepts could also solve the incompleteness of the VID in regard to the relationship between the physical and textual manifestations of charters, as well as diplomatic formulas and particular charter contents.

VID 88 (*Une mention*--“la simple indication de l'existence d'un document”; acts mentioned; erwähnte Dokumente) should be expanded by a distinction between those which are still preserved and those which are lost without any kind of surviving textual tradition. The latter are **deperdita** (VID_add_5), i.e. documents not existing anymore in any kind of tradition, but mentioned or clearly referenced in other acts or written sources, from which we can conclude their former existence. A *deperditum* should further be kept distinct from a document that was lost after reliable publication in a scholarly edition, a formal description or even a photograph--**missing after being published**; dt. verschollen nach (wissenschaftlicher) Veröffentlichung (VID_add_6). Both forms allow the more or less complete reconstruction of contents and/or diplomatic features of missing acts.¹⁸

VID 97 (*Les actes antérieurs ou retroacta*; *Vorurkunden*; previous acts) describe only one direction in the sequence of documents referencing other charters. **Following acts** (dt. Nachurkunden, VID_add_7) as any kind of mentioning would describe the whole “family of acts” concerning one addressee or topic. Following acts go beyond explicit references of the written act, but include all charters referencing the legal act documented in the charter in question.¹⁹

¹⁸ E.g. the charter of despot of Serbia Stefan Lazarevic (cca. 1405) to the city of Belgrade is not preserved in any kind of diplomatic tradition, but was mentioned by Stefan’s biographer Konstantin Philosoph, who retells (or cites?) one part of the expositio. Also the lost charter of King Vladislav (1233/34–42/43) to the monastery of Mileseva was mentioned in the late transcript of a forgery made probably in the 15th century as the single direct evidence of the once doubtless issued founding donation of that ruler to his endowment (Mladenovic 2007, 347; Vujosevic 2020--Cetinje, Stefan). On the other hand, the nine charters taken from the monastery of Hilandar in 1931, after they had been published and photographed, and afterwards gone lost (Bubalo 2014, 77) shouldn’t be regarded as *deperdita*.

¹⁹ As for instance in the case the Serbian king Milutin confirmed the charter of the “young king” Stefan for the Monastery Vranjina on Scutari sea, without mentioning his rebelled and in the meantime ousted son and his legal act: Vujosevic 2020--Cetinje, Milutin.

Self appellation (of the given document, e.g. “Privilegium”, “Littera”, “Chrysobull” etc; dt. Selbstbezeichnung, VID_add_8)--expresses the (mostly unsystematically) developed terminology of acts used by issuers/scribes, which can be of a crucial importance for scholarship, especially in dealing with often unclear typology of documents, or with contemporary concepts relating to medieval chancelleries.²⁰ The term may also be missing or given in a “descriptive” form (“questo scripto”, “in premissis”...). This “self appellation” is not covered by the VID as a separate concept but only in the terminology for individual forms in the section V. “Nature diplomatique des acts” (nos. 382-420) and its subsection “Classification des lettre” (nos. 421-423). A full semantic web extension of the VID could include a property that relates the text given in the document itself with any kind of controlled vocabulary like the terms given in the above mentioned section.

Recording note / writing note (dt. Schreibervermerk, VID_add_9) and **recording order** (dt. Beurkundungsbefehl, VID_add_10) – the phrases containing information about the scribe, dictator or circumstances of writing/issuing the document (e.g. “written by NN on behalf of NN, validated by NN”). The entry VID 180 considers such notes indeed, but only as “hors teneur” (extra tenorem/sigillum), explaining that they “ne participent pas stricto sensu à la nature même de l'acte”. In our opinion, this pure formalistic view could be enhanced with the content-related one, which then “allows” such notes to be placed both “within” and “outside” the actual text of the document.

Some parts of the charters’ *dispositio* should be recognised as text passages (sections), irrespective of the fact if they are expressed in specific formula or not. Such cases are **list of pertinents** (dt. Pertinenzliste, VID_add_20) in the sense of listing the given or confirmed possessions to a recipient and **description of borders** (dt. Grenzbeschreibung, VID_add_19), which mean specifying topographic data in order to define the area of the estates in question. As the VID offers only the “pertinents clause” (*La formule de pertinence*--204) and gives no entry concerning borders at all, these could be added as narrower concepts to VID 198 (*Le dispositif*), in this case describing a part-whole-relationship.

An extension of the VID comes in particular into play, when broadening the geographical and cultural horizon. From the experience in the Byzantine and (multilingual) South Slavic diplomatics we consider the following new concepts as generic descriptive categories to be a good extension of the VID:

Language (of the given document; dt. Sprache, VID_add_21) – indicates the language of the witness in question, which also may not be the language of the (preserved or not preserved) original. In such cases of secondary traditions in the form of translations, the primary language should be mentioned (e.g. “Latin, originally

²⁰ On self appellation of Serbian documents: Bubalo (2014) 55-64; cf. Maksimovic (1999), 34-35. For the Byzantine chancery see: Dölger, Karayannopoulos (1968) 24-25; Oikonomidès (1985) 190-193; *Oxford Handbook* (2008) 129-135 (Müller).

Serbian”). Belonging in the VID structure to “Caractères internes”, it should be added as a subterm to VID 162.

Script (dt. Schrift, VID_add_22) – gives the general identification of the script (e.g. Latin, Greek, Cyrillic). It would find its place within “Caractères externes” (VID 132-161), maybe under VID 159 (*Une écriture de chancellerie*). Individual **style / script type** (of lettering; dt. Schriftart), which gives the general palaeographical classification of the script (e.g. majuscule, minuscule etc), should be subject to a controlled vocabulary of palaeographical terms.²¹

Further gaps become obvious when looking at non-western-European diplomatics, particularly Byzantine chancery traditions, which also exerted strong influence on the diplomatic practices of Southeastern European countries in the late middle ages (especially Serbia and Bulgaria, but also Wallachia and Moldavia).²² Following that, two terms in the field of formulas and external features respectively should be added:

Logos-formula (dt. Logos-Formel) – the art of validation/recognition mostly of solemn donation charters, consisting normally of „ΛΟΓΟΣ“ (“word”) repeated three times in different places in the document. As a rule, the term was inscribed in red ink, using three cases in exact succession (accusative, genitive, nominative).²³ Possible solutions would be to put this entry into VID as a subterm (VID_add_11) either of *Une formule* (VID 183) or *Le seing manuel* (VID 258; not VID 151 concerning “notaires publics”), as Logos-formula was written down by issuer himself or his logothete.

Red inked (or special coloured) letters and signs (dt. rote oder besonders gefärbte Buchstaben und Zeichen, VID_add_12) – were in Southeast European diplomatics mainly reserved for emperor’s signature, logos-formula or invocatio symbolica, while other colours were applied only in particular cases (such as green for signatures of Serbian church principals: archbishops and—later—patriarchs).²⁴ This new entry should be distinguished from the already existing “lettre ornée” (*Zierbuchstabe*--decorated letter, VID 161), which relates to the form of letters and not to their colour.

²¹ A possible starting point for this could be the RDF representation of the glossary of the palaeographical e-learning resource *palaeographie-online.de*: <http://www.palaeographie-online.de/rdf/>.

²² See Lascaris (1931) 500-510. Detailed on Byzantine influences on the Serbian diplomatics: Dölger (1961) 83-103.

²³ On logos-formula see Dölger, Karayannopoulos (1968) 35, 117–118 (“Logos-Wort”) and in detail Oikonomidès (1985) 180–183. Its mostly constant structure was not adopted consequently in Serbia, as apart from translation „СЛОВО“ also other terms appear, such as emperor title, and moreover regardless the succession of the cases (on logos-formula in Serbian diplomatics see Porcic 2016, 265-266). Interestingly, another specific formula of subscription/validation in the Byzantine diplomatics has found its place in the VID nomenclature: the menologem (VID 158), consisting of the month and indiction of issuing, also engrossed in red ink. On menologem see Dölger, Karayannopoulos (1968) 53 and Porcic (2015) 285-298. for use in Serbia.

²⁴ On using red letters and signs in Serbian diplomatics: Porcic (2016) 255-273 (cf. Vujosevic et al. 2014, 141, note 14).

Byzantine diplomatics has its own terminology, but it substantially overlaps with that of the VID (especially concerning the structure of charters; cf. Oxford handbook of Byzantine studies 2008--Müller, Poulimenou et al. 2009). The similarities are significant enough that they could be represented by the VID, in particular in cases of terms applying to same phenomena (e.g. proemium/arenga--http://www.cei.lmu.de/VID/#VID_196_bis). Some specific features already exist in the VID nomenclature (*menologem*, see footnote 23 above). The new concepts fit easily into the organisation of the terms in the VIS: further extensions beyond the Logos-formula mentioned above would concern characteristic formulas like **Κράτος** (/our/ authority/governance) as the first word of the last line of the diploma announcing the signature (VID_add_13), or **Διά τοῦ** (by/through) as the phrase probably indicating the intervener/petitioner (VID_add_24). They could be added to the section on the elements of diplomatic discourse.²⁵

The extension of the VID with concepts from non-western-european diplomatic cultures could be applied to Ottoman, Tibetan, Chinese, Ethiopian diplomatics (Vogeler 2018) and, in fact, scholars of Ottoman and Tibetan diplomatics have reused Latin terminology as described by the VID (Schuh 1978, 411-425; Fekete 1926, XII-XIII; Reychmann & Zajackowski 1968. 139-141).

3. Conceptual modifications

Some of the existing VID definitions seem to need conceptual modifications. For instance, the critique by Große (1996) that including charters of territorial princes as “actes publics” (VID 8a) contradicts the German tradition of distinguishing between papal, royal and imperial charters on the one hand and all others as “Privaturkunden” on the other (Alfred Gawlik in LexMA VII, col. 222-224), might be solvable by adding a dedicated entry for **charters of territorial princes** as a subterm to both (VID_add_26).²⁶ The introduction of the clear distinction between *vidimus* and *transsumpt* established in German diplomatics (Joachim Spiegel in LexMA VIII, col. 952f. and col. 1636f.) would require a considerable rephrasing of VID 66-69.

In other cases existing definitions need to be clarified. The definition of VID 53 (*Une copie*) distinguishes only two types of copies: the authentic copy (VID 54) and the informal copy (VID 55): “Une copie (lat.: copia, exemplum, transcriptum, transumptum) est une transcription littérale d'un texte antérieur. Une copie peut être *authentique ou *informe”. This is insufficient, if the historical authenticity of the copies is considered: Diplomats can come to the conclusion that an informal copy

²⁵ On “Κράτος” see Poulimenou et al (2009) 97; on “Διά τοῦ” see Karayannopoulos (1998) 203–232 (cf. Vujosevic 2019, Clergy, 78-79).

²⁶ Also in Serbia documents of local princes or territorial rulers (after the collapse of the empire in 1371) are considered as “official” (“actes publics”); cf. for instance the respective approach in the recent edition Porcic--Isailovic (2019) 15-16.

is *credible* (de: „glaubwürdig”) even if not formally authenticated.²⁷ A credible copy reproduces the legal act in its core, although it cannot be taken as a reproduction of textual or even physical form. It does not invent legal facts or modifies legal facts as they were stated in the original. This adds a historical facet to the formal definitions of the copy, following the distinction between VID 116 and VID 123 as subconcepts to VID 111 (*faux*): The complete forgery (VID 116) is formally but also substantially forged and reports invented legal facts, while a “diplomatic” forgery (VID 123) may report credible historical information in a form not fitting to the chancery practice or produced outside the chancery (including *acte établi hors chancellerie*--VID 267, *copie figurée/Nachzeichnung*--VID 56 and *pseudo-original*--VID 117 as subterms). The relationship between historical and formal authenticity can be expressed with VID after clarifying that the definition of VID 110 keeps historical credibility independent from diplomatic authenticity. With this kind of specification the “credible copy” would fall into the combined scope of VID 53 and VID 110.

VID chapter VI (“Nature juridique des actes”) could sharpen its conceptual profile: if the term ‘acte’ in VID 424-501 is understood as a single document, it would exclude charters which often contain several of the subjects listed here in one and the same document. This structural change can best be achieved by modifying the existing definition of VID 424, adding a note on the scope of the concept. This note can explain that the concept deals with legal acts in the sense of VID 4 (*Un acte juridique*) and that VID 424 is an extension of VID 6-12, which means that a single written act can include many legal acts. Hence, the acts described in the following entries (425-501) do not have to correspond with a specific diplomatic form, which is described in VID 385-420.

The VID chapter VI would then have to include additional concepts like:

Confirmation (of rights, possessions); dt. Bestätigung (VID_add_17)--which means a legal act of confirmation itself and should be distinct from VID 7c (“acte confirmatif, Bestätigungsurkunde”) as document type. It could reuse a part of the definition of VID 51 (“confirmation, Bestätigung”): “Une confirmation (lat.: confirmatio) est une décision par laquelle sont renouvelées des mesures qui ont été précédemment consignées dans des actes antérieurs.”

Privilege (of immunity); dt. Immunitätsprivileg (VID_add_18)--which means a legal act of giving respective immunities and should be distinct from VID 395 (“le privilège d’immunité”) as document type according to its “diplomatic nature” (see above).

Judgment (sentence); dt. Urteil, Richterspruch (VID_add_25)--an official decision solving a legal dispute, given by the actor such as defined in the charter text. As neither VID chapter I nor V offer any entry considering this kind of action, the added

²⁷ See Vujosevic--AfD (2020), 248-249 for Serbia, including some examples.

concept should consider both possible meanings of Judgment: as a single legal act and as a document type.

Hence, we propose keeping all entries of the VID chapter VI as they are, but considering their modified definition as both document type and single legal act expressed in one document (e.g. VID 425--*Une donation*; VID 436--*Une fondation*; VID 486--*Un acte d'échange*).

XML-TEI

As described above, XML has been used to encode charters since the early 21st century. The XML schemata proposed by Poulimenou et al. and Ansani (CDLM) are generic enough that they could have been used for charter encoding, but they have never been reused. The only diplomatics related XML schema which has found wider distribution is the CEI.

Many of the elements in these schemata are well covered by the guidelines of the TEI. To name just a few: cdlm:TIT-DOC maps to tei:head, cdlm:NUMERO to tei:idno, cdlm:REG maps to tei:abstract, cdlm:TXT to tei:q or tei:foreign, cdlm:TRADITIO to tei:listWit, cdlm:BIBLIO to tei:listBibl, cdlm:P to tei:p, cdlm:NOTA to tei:note, cdlm:PERSONA to tei:persName etc. The same is true for the CEI.²⁸ But these elements describe all generic textual features. How can we build an extension of the TEI covering the needs of diplomatists? Vogeler 2015 argued that we could add elements to the TEI representing the concepts diplomatics is interested in, and thus extend the TEI to cover legal documents better than it does currently. Recently, he and Sean Winslow described the conversion from CEI encoding to TEI encoding, identifying elements which should be added to the TEI (<https://github.com/GVogeler/CEI2TEI>).

However, if we accept that the dedicated diplomatics element names fit better into the context of the VID's attempts to clarify terminology than into the definition of a text encoding schema, we can come to a different proposal: using the existing generic TEI elements and assigning the diplomatic semantics to them via the @ana attribute (e.g. instead of <arenga> one could use <div ana="vid:196bis">). Francisco Alvarez Carbajal has suggested this approach already in 2015.

The prefixing mechanism of the TEI helps to handle this specialisation of existing TEI elements in the @ana-attribute: the <prefixDef>-element allows to define the vid:-prefix to be replaced by the string `http://www.cei.lmu.de/VID/#VID_` which is the same for all VID-URIs:

²⁸ See in particular the conversion script at <https://github.com/GVogeler/CEI2TEI/blob/master/workflow.xsl>

```
<prefixDef ident="vid" matchPattern="([a-z]+)"
replacementPattern="http://www.cei.lmu.de/VID/#VID_§1"><p>The
SKOS definitions of the Vocabulaire international de la
diplomatie, ed. Maria Milagros Cárcel Ortí, 2. ed., València
1997 (Collecció Oberta) as referenced in <gi>@type</gi> or
<gi>@ana</gi> attributes are referenced by using the prefix
<code>vid:</code> and the identifier (usually the number of
the entry, please refer to http://www.cei.lmu.de/VID/skos/ for
further details).</p>
</prefixDef>
```

This method would even include extending the definitions of the VID as the common ground by proposals from the community with their own URIs: using a different prefix referencing the project specific SKOS terminology. It might look practical to some projects referencing these external definitions in the @type attribute, in particular, when the VID extension seems to be a specialisation of the TEI semantics. But still, we suggest using the @ana-attribute for two reasons: 1. it is defined globally, so it can be applied to any TEI element; 2. it is the main method used to apply stand-off annotation (<https://tei-c.org/release/doc/tei-p5-doc/en/html/AI.html#AIATTS>).

This leads to the question of how a **prototypical charter edition** could be expressed using TEI elements. The most obvious application of XML to charter texts is the diplomatic discourse: legal acts have a quite formulaic language which is highly structured. Markup should be able to encode this. The closest elements in the TEI seem to be those used for letters (*opener*, *closer*, *salute*, *signed*), as they share the epistolary tradition with medieval charters. However, the definitions of them are close to a letter model used since the 18th century, so we prefer to use generic text structure elements like *div/ab/seg* to describe medieval charters. But even those carry semantic and formal challenges.

A formal challenge is the XML nesting defined by the TEI schema that allows self-containment only on the *div* and the *seg* level, but does not allow text in *div* or the *seg*-element directly at <body> level. Considering the definitions and the contexts given to the elements in question, the use of the *div*-element fits very well for marking-up of the main diplomatic structure as *protocol*, *context*, and *eschatocol* and the *ab*-element for substructures like *invocatio*, *arenga*, *narratio*, *intitulatio*, *sanctio*, *datatio* and *subscriptio*, as <ab> allows further inclusion of substructures (<seg>) like single clauses, and remains thus flexible. Let us explain this a bit more in detail.

The main textual model of the TEI is based on 19th century printed typography. This includes a very well established concept of relationships between logical and visual structure, condensed in the concept of the “paragraph”:

<https://github.com/TEIC/TEI/issues/1929>. In TEI-P5, the TEI community realised that there are textual cultures in which these connections are less obvious: they structure

text visually without claiming that this is “the smallest regular unit into which prose can be divided”. In the TEI community these concepts are still under discussion. In this discussion, examples from manuscript culture and from documentary writing support the need for textual structure that is not very well covered by the current definitions in the TEI Guidelines: <https://github.com/TEIC/TEI/issues/1856>, <https://github.com/TEIC/TEI/issues/1929>, <http://tei-l.970651.n3.nabble.com/lt-ab-gt-within-lt-ab-gt-td4026246.html>. This raises the question of whether the core concepts of diplomatic discourse can easily be projected on the TEI concepts.

Sean Winslow's proposal for the mapping of the CEI on the TEI avoids this discussion by generalising any kind of textual structure into an element “diploPart” (https://github.com/GVogeler/CEI2TEI/blob/902b3210ca6455e916ef56a0f15344735d030158/tei_cei.odd#L411-L550). This gives the advantage of remaining flexible in nesting. In fact, we assume, that continuing the discussion will bring forward the specific characteristics of the diplomatic discourse--its relationship to epistolary theory, to legal language, and, of course, its own cultural history--but will not change the fact, that the textual structure offered by the TEI encoding only loosely models the historical reality of diplomatics.

Before the TEI council has accepted Winslow’s proposal, the transfer of TEI concepts to the diplomatic structure can best be achieved with a logical interpretation of `div/ab/seg`. We believe that a representation of a logical unit “similar to a paragraph but without the semantic baggage of the paragraph”, as `<ab>` is defined, reflects the importance charter authors gave to units of discourse as parts which can be clearly distinguished, but do not (always) have a visual representation (such as *littera elongata* for instance) and sometimes even are not reflected in grammar. For instance, the papal charter uses “`<intitulatio>`Honorius episcopus servus servorum domini`</intitulatio>` `<salutatio>`salutem et apostolicam benedictionem`</salutatio>`” as a grammatical ellipse. The same is true for most of the dating clauses, simply introduced with *datum et actum*. The logical encoding makes sense in particular when there are also visual representations of documents, such as photos or scans conveying the layout of the text. However, the reference to the VID gives room for alternative interpretations of the linguistic structure of the charter. So it does not matter if somebody prefers `ab/seg/seg` or any other three-level hierarchy, since the `@ana` reference points to the same diplomatic structure represented in semantic web VID.

With the help of the `@ana`-attribute we can integrate semantic web annotation into the XML annotation. It is not the TEI definition of XML elements, but URI given in the `@ana`-attribute which defines the diplomatic structure. Accordingly, in a semantic web approach to the diplomatic encoding, the discussion about the best fitting TEI encoding does not have to be concluded. We can consider the linguistic structure to be represented by the TEI as separate from diplomatic discourse and focus on

modelling of the discourse itself. Finally, nesting elements with the same name is in the risk of clouding the structure, so for practical purposes we suggest using `<div>` for macrostructure, `<ab>` for textual patterns which the scribes separated into clearly distinguishable text blocks, and `<seg>` for structures contained in these anonymous blocks. To all of these, we suggest adding the analytical reference in `@ana`-attribute referring to formal definitions as RDF-URIs as provided by the VID-SKOS. The TEI in listing 1 gives an example of this approach.²⁹

```

<text>
  <body>
    <div ana="VID:add_16"><!-- cadre formel - protocole -->
      <ab ana="VID:146"><!-- invocation figurée/symbolique --></ab>
      <ab ana="VID:196bis"><!-- préambule -->Понѣже оубо чловѣколюбць
      Богъ неизреченною моудростію и промыслѡмъ оустрааѣ вьса [...]
      светителя же и чюдотворца Савоу, бльжнѣаго ходатааа ѡ насъ къ
      Богу.</ab>
      <ab ana="VID:197"><!-- exposé (narratio) -->Тѣмже и<seg
      ana="VID:187"><!-- suscription (intitulatio) -->азь, въ Христа Бога
      благовѣрныи и христѡлюбивіи самодръжць Срьблѣмъ и Грькомъ, Стефанъ
      царь,</seg>божѣствомъ любовію раждигаемъ, прїидохъ въ Светою Гору
      аѡнскою [...] и благословеніе прїемъ ѡт светыхъ и чьстныхихъ и
      аггеломъ подобныхъ житіемъ ѡтць. <seg ana="VID:438"><!-- dotation
      d'église -->И елико бысть моштно царьствоу ми, оукрасихъ светые и
      чьстные храмы ѡт малыхъ даже и до великыхъ, ово златіими съсоуди и
      срьбрьними, ово же свештенными одѣждами [...] и прѣподобнаго игоумена
      квръ Гьрвасіа и съ братіаи ѡдаровахъ,</seg> такоже мольбники юже къ
      Богу ѡ нашемъ спасенію и дръжавѣ царьства.</ab>
      <ab ana="VID:319"><!-- requête (petitio) -->Прїидѣ же къ мнѣ
      игоумень квръ Гьрвасіе съ чьстнымъ съборомъ лавры хиландарские
      [...]. И принесоше <seg ana="VID:97"><!-- actes antérieurs
      (Vorurkunden) -->хрисовоуле за Зигъ и за мѣсто зовомею Скорьпіа.
      </seg></ab>
    </div>
    <div ana="VID:198"><!-- dispositif -->
      <ab ana="VID:484"><!-- vente -->[...] и изволи се царьствоу ми
      [...] еже коупити ми то [...] и приложити прѣсветѣи владычици нашей
      Богородици хиландарьской. [...] изнаидоше мегѣ и синоре.</ab>
      <ab ana="VID:add_19"><!-- description of borders -->Прьви
      синоръ починѣ ѡт вьстока [...] на два камена становита подь брьдо,
      ѡткле ѡвьи синоръ починѣ.</ab>
      <ab ana="VID:263"><!-- liste des témoins -->И иже се обрѣтоше
      тогда на съборѣ, записа и тѣхъ имена царьство ми въ сіемъ <seg
      ana="VID:add_8"><!-- self appellation -->златопечатленемъ
      хрисовоуле</seg> въ оувѣденіе: чьстны прѡть Светые Гори, Гьрманъ
      перомонахъ [...] Дїѡнвсіеви обьтѣли ѡевдосіе перомонахъ.</ab>
      <ab ana="VID:246"><!-- corroboration -->И сіе приложи царьство
      ми и оутврѣди съ <seg ana="VID:add_8"><!-- self appellation --

```

²⁹ An excerpt with reduced markup (without line breaks, names, critical apparatus etc.). The presented charter is the lost witness ("missing after being published", see above, p. 9) of a forgery attributed to emperor Stefan Dusan, with the issuing date 12 December 1347 (edition according to DSD; complete printed edition: Miklosich 1858, 124-128; commentary in comparison with the preserved copy: Fostikov 2017).

```

>златопечатнымъ словѣмъ</seg> съ чьстнымъ съборомъ Светые Горы, да
ѣсть въ область прѣсветѣи владычици нашей [...] ѡт насъ и до
вѣка.</ab>
</div>
<div ana="VID:182a"><!-- cadre formel - eschatocole -->
  <ab ana="VID:211"><!-- appel aux successeurs -->Молю же и васъ,
ѣгоже Богъ изволить царьствовати по насъ [...] нѣ паче потврѣжденну
и испльнюю.</ab>
  <ab ana="VID:237"><!-- clauses pénales (sanctio) -->Аште ли кто
дрьзнеть потворити или разорити сѣе наше приношеніе и даръ
[...]</ab>
  <ab ana="VID:561"><!-- formule de date -->Записа се сѣе [...]
<seg ana="VID:562"><!-- date chronique -->въ лѣто .#swns., мѣсеца
декеврѣа .в1. днь, индиктиѡнь .а.,</seg> <seg ana="VID:563"><!--
date topographique -->на Прѣвѣлацѣ.</seg></ab>
  <ab ana="VID:259" xml:id="signature"><!-- signature --> СТЕФАНЪ
ВЪ ХРИСТА БОГА БЛАГОВѣРНЫ ЦАРЬ И САМОДРЪЖЬЦЪ СРЪБЛѢМЪ И ГРЪКОМЪ И
ВЛЪГАРОМЪ</ab>
</div>
<div ana="VID:347"><!-- notes dorsales, marginales -->
  <ab n="1" ana="VID:add_14"><!-- notes dorsales --
>...атрѡса...</ab>
  <ab n="2" ana="VID:add_14"><!-- notes dorsales -->Куметица...
Зигос...</ab>
  <ab n="3" ana="VID:add_14"><!-- notes dorsales -->+ Цара
Стефана рисовуль за Куметицу</ab>
  <ab n="4" ana="VID:add_14"><!-- notes dorsales -->Ισον τοῦ
χρισσοβούλω τοῦ Στεφάνου περὶ τῆς Κομῆτιτζας σερβικῶ</ab>
</div>
</body>
</text>

```

Listing 1: TEI/XML encoding with reference to the VID

Other diplomatic phenomena appear as metadata in the `teiHeader`, demonstrated in listing 2 below. The application of the `teiHeader` is straightforward for features like the language of the charter (`VID_add_21`) which can be expressed as `tei:textLang`. The same is true for physical features like the writing support (`tei:support`) or the date and place of creation (`tei:origDate` and `tei:origPlace`).

The example from the project *Diplomatarium Serbicum Digitale* demonstrates a case where standard TEI is not sufficient: the editorial practice of Serbian royal documents has established a **formalised heading** of each document, for instance. This is a combination of the date, the author and an internal ID (e.g. “134804xx taq Dusan (262)”). It fits very well into the definition of the `titleStmt/title` in the `teiHeader`. As all the parts of this title are encoded elsewhere, the practice could make use of the `@sameAs` encoding using empty elements pointing to the `xml:id` of the main

definition of the content (e.g. `<placeName sameAs="#origPlace"/>` as shown in listing 2 below).

Concerning various textual witnesses, diplomatics has its own system in the description of relationships between them. We have stated above the need to extend the concepts of the VID with distinctions for credibility of copies. The TEI offers the `<filiation>`-element to describe these relationships suggesting a generic terminology drawn from textual scholarship: *antigraph*, *apograph*, and *protograph*. These do not reflect on the legal content of the document. An encoding enhancing the TEI markup with references to the (extended) VID can solve this problem: `<filiation ana="VID:24"(tradition des actes)><term ana="VID:53 VID:110">Credible copy</term></filiation>` refers to a description of the filiation in terms of diplomatics.

Sean Winslow (2018, 2020–2022) has discussed the relevance of authentication in the conceptualisation of diplomatists and suggests a generic element `tei:authen` accompanied by a controlled vocabulary for the methods of authentication.³⁰ This vocabulary even contains references to the VID. There are strong arguments in favour of the introduction of this element into the TEI, but it has not yet happened. A generic TEI construct like `profileDesc/settingDesc/ab[@ana='vid:9a']` references the VID-definition of any markup authentication, or `vid:369` as the act of authentication itself. The TEI provides an element for seals (`<sealDesc>`), which can be annotated with `@ana='vid:9a'` to describe the legal function of the physical object. However, we propose to separate the information about the physical object from its legal function. A dedicated structure for validation marks as part of the `<settingDesc>` referencing `VID:9a` can describe expected but missing validation marks with empty elements. They reference the physical or textual manifestation with `@sameAs`. The content of this element could relay via a `tei:term` encoding to the appropriate VID terms to describe the means of authentication (e.g. `vid:255`: notarial subscription, `vid:502`: seal). The `tei:signed` element from the letter model has a clearly different scope, as the TEI defines it as a closing salutation, not as a signature creating binding legal acts. Thus, signatures in the text are better encoded referencing `vid:259` (signature).

The use of **red letters** in the charters can be described generally in the TEI element `<decoDesc>`. This could trigger a discussion if red letters should better not be conceptualised as „decoration” but as a means of “authentication”. However, the reference to the VID assigns the correct semantics in the terms of diplomatics. A single `decoNote` can contain prose for an overall description. Putting the `@ana` attribute with a URI of an extended VID (`vid:add_12`) this description would link directly to text where the use of `<hi>` with the same URI. In fact, the semantic web approach could be here extended beyond the use of `@type` and `@ana` to the use of `@rendition`, which the TEI defines as a reference to a description of the visual form of the element in the source text (TEI Consortium 2020).

³⁰ <https://github.com/GVogeler/CEI2TEI/blob/master/Authentication/authen.skos.ttl>

A similar approach can be taken for **graphical signs** like *invocatio symbolica*, *signum recognitionis* (ruche) etc. A <decoNote> referring to vid:145 in the @ana-attribute can contain general descriptions for the same phenomena which can be encoded as *figure* in the text. The formal definition of narrower concepts in the VID as suggested above would even allow specialised description of the graphical signs in the text still linking them to the general description in decoNote.

The description of the **document date** can use enhanced TEI encoding as well. While msDesc//origDate und msDesc//origPlace are a good fit for the creation of an original document when production of the physical object and the legal act coincide (as they usually do), they are misleading when used for forgeries and (interpolated) copies. In the TEI semantics the origDate and origPlace describe the origin of the manuscript, which in case of a forgery is different from the pretended date of the legal act. The reference to the vid:562 and vid:563 adds encoding of the date given in the document. A forgery or a copy would thus have at least two dating elements: one with the @ana=vid:562 and @ana=vid:563 referencing the date and place given in the document (encoded within text//body) and another one following the TEI semantics for the creation of the physical document (origDate and origPlace within msDesc//history), i.e. the date of the forgery / copy. As stated above, VID 560 can be used for the concepts of inferred date and place of issuing, if dating elements in the document itself are missing and the researcher is able to reconstruct the date and place of the original. This information could be given within titleStmnt/title (see p. 8 above).

The semantic web is based on the open world-assumption, meaning that a non-existing data point is only considered as not known, not as proven to be non-existent. This can create problems in case of features which are expected but reliably not existent, e.g. the logos-formula, or seal. Also in terms of document description (within msIdentifier, for instance) there are cases of non-existing signatures of archival units. The TEI encoding should therefore offer a category for this kind of description with content stating the non-existence explicitly. In Byzantine (and Serbian) diplomatics, the existence of the logos-formula is an example of this situation, as it normally identifies the Chrysobull / Chrysobullos logos charter type and is a kind of validation or authentication--so its absence would be an important info with implications regarding (debated) authenticity and/or credibility of the document.

Generally, the encoding has to provide methods to describe the absence of an expected diplomatic feature (seal, signature etc.). Sometimes a verbal description is sufficient. For cases, in which a formal distinction is necessary, the standard approach in TEI/XML encoding is using empty elements. <settingDesc><p ana="vid:add_11"/></settingDesc> would describe a document, in which a

logos-formula is expected, but not existent. Further comments on this can be inserted as `<note>` elements. This is not possible in cases when there is information about the non-existent object, e.g. with lost seals, where the text of the charter often suggests the owner of the seal. We propose adding a generic term for lost objects of diplomatic relevance as `vid:add_27` and using it in the `@ana`-attribute of the appropriate TEI element (e.g. `<seal ana="vid:9a vid:add_27"><!-- description of the seal --></seal>`).

Finally, the VID is particularly useful when it comes to **classifying documents**. The TEI offers the element `textClass` to describe the genre of the text with keywords. These can reference the VID in another attribute fit to create links to external resource: `term/@ref` is defined in the TEI precisely to solve situations like this. Referencing the self appellation would be made possible by a keywords element referencing the `vid:add_8`.

The diplomatic phenomena appearing as metadata could be presented in the `teiHeader` according to following example:³¹

```
<teiHeader>
  <fileDesc>
    <titleStmt>
      <title><idno>134804xx taq Dusan (262)</idno> <term
ana="VID:385"><!-- charte -->Charter</term> of <persName
ana="VID:16"><!-- auteur d'un acte écrit -->Emperor Dusan</persName>
to <orgName ana="VID:17"><!-- destinataire -->Hilandar</orgName>
confirming all its possessions (<placeName ana="VID:563"
sameAs="#origPlace"/><date ana="VID:560"><!-- date -->January-April
1348</date>)</title>
    </titleStmt>
    <sourceDesc>
      <listWit>
        <witness>
          <msDesc>
            <msIdentifier>
              <settlement>Belgrade</settlement>
              <repository>Museum of the Serbian Orthodox
Church</repository>
              <idno ana="VID:add_27"></idno>
            </msIdentifier>
            <msContents>
              <textLang>Serbian</textLang>
              <msItem>
                <filiation ana="VID:24"><!-- tradition des actes --
><term ana="VID:53 VID:110">Credible copy</term></filiation>
              </msItem>
            </msContents>
          </msDesc>
        </witness>
      </listWit>
    </sourceDesc>
  </fileDesc>
</teiHeader>
```

³¹ The presented document is the so-called "general" charter of emperor Stefan Dusan to Hilandar with the confirmation of all possessions of the Serbian monastery, issued in the first months of 1348 (source for the metadata: DSD unit 134804xx taq Dusan (262) translated into English). According to the literature, the preserved witness is regarded as a credible copy (last printed edition with commentary: Misić-Koprivica, 2015).

```

</msContents>
<physDesc>
  <objectDesc>
    <supportDesc>
      <support>
        <material>parchment</material>
      </support>
    <extent>
      <dimensions unit="mm">
        <height>1920</height>
        <width>370</width>
      </dimensions>
    </extent>
    <condition>Spots and paleness in places, which
only slightly impede reading</condition>
  </supportDesc>
</objectDesc>
<scriptDesc>
  <scriptNote><!-- script --><term
ana="VID:add_22">Cyrillic</term> <term ana="VID:add_23"><!-- style --
>Uncial script</term></scriptNote>
  </scriptDesc>
  <decoDesc>
    <decoNote ana="VID:add_12"><!-- red letters --
>Cross of the invocatio symbolica, initial, signature</decoNote>
    <decoNote ana="VID:145"><!-- éléments figurés --
>NIKA-cross of the invocatio symbolica, cross before the
signature</decoNote>
  </decoDesc>
  <sealDesc ana="VID:540 VID:add_27" xml:id="sd1"><!--
sceau pendant -->
    <condition>
      <p>The seal itself is lost.</p>
      <p>Red string through holes on the left half of
the signature. Mention: „Chrysobull“. According to Safarik's
indication [...] the charter had a „pendant golden seal“.</p>
    </condition>
  </sealDesc>
</physDesc>
<history>
  <origin><origPlace
xml:id="origPlace">Hilandar</origPlace><origDate>Around
1365?</origDate></origin><provenance>The charter was removed from
the monastery around 1760 [...] kept since 1946 [in the Museum] in
the building of the Patriarchy.</provenance>
</history>
  <additional>
    <surrogates><list type="photographs"><item>Collection
of Vladimir Mosin, unknown location (black-white,
unclear)</item></list></surrogates>
  </additional>
</msDesc>
</witness>
</listWit>
<listBibl ana="VID:19"><!-- édition diplomatique -->

```

```

    <bibl>P. J. Schaffarik, Serbische Lesekörner
[...]</bibl><bibl>A. Востоков, Описание русскихъ и словенскихъ
рукописей [...]</bibl>[...]
  </listBibl>
  <listBibl type="literature">
    <bibl>P. J. Schaffarik, Übersicht der vorzüglichsten
schriftlichen Denkmäler [...]</bibl>[...]<bibl>М. Живојиновић,
Властелинство манастира Хиландара [...]</bibl>[...]
  </listBibl>
</sourceDesc>
</fileDesc>
<profileDesc>
  <textClass>
    <keywords ana="VID:385">
      <term>Charter</term>
    </keywords>
    <keywords ana="VID:add_8"><!-- self appellation -->
      <term>Хрисовуљ</term>
    </keywords>
  </textClass>
  <abstract>
    <p>Emperor Stefan Dusan with his consort Empress Jelena
[...] donates to the monastery of Hilandar [...]</p>
  </abstract>
  <settingDesc><ab ana="vid:9a"><!-- marques de validation --
><seg ana="vid:add_11"/><!-- logos formula missing --><seg
ana="vid:259" sameAs="#signature"/><seg ana="vid:502"
sameAs="#sd1"/><!-- seal missing --></settingDesc>
  <handNotes ana="VID:347">
    <handNote><locus ana="VID:add_15"><!-- notes marginales -->At
left margin in the fifth sixth of the document 2,5 rotated
lines</locus> <term type="genre">Short
summary</objectType><origDate>Second half of the 18th
century</origDate></handNote>
  </handNotes>
</profileDesc>
</teiHeader>

```

Listing 2: Example for a XML/TEI metadata section (teiHeader) enriched with VID terminology

Conclusion

Digital diplomatics, as pioneered by Michael Gervers, is about converting diplomatics knowledge into digital form. The digital representation of the VID is a crucial step in this process as it formalises a wide range of diplomatics knowledge. We identified some problems of the VID which could be solved by extending it with new concepts and by reorganising it in more significant hierarchies. The semantic web version of the VID as it is available in SKOS at <http://www.cei.lmu.de/VID/> allows for these

changes: reorganising the VID with appropriate skos:narrower references and several new concepts are just an addition in the RDF representation. Changing existing definitions is more complicated, as we would have to keep track of the versions to establish citability. The updated VID version would probably use a new namespace for the updated concepts (<http://www.cei.lmu.de/VID/1.1/> for instance). But digital diplomatics and the semantic web should reduce the technical workload, so diplomatists can concentrate on intellectual work. Setting up a group of experts taking care of how to modify and extend the VID consistently would be a great activity for the Commission Internationale de Diplomatique (CID).

XML has been proven to be an efficient technology to create scholarly editions, in general and for diplomatics scholarly editions as well. The need for domain specific vocabularies has triggered several solutions expressed in XML, while at the same time the TEI has established itself as the main reference for XML encoding of humanities textual resources. The approach of the CEI to enhance the TEI by dedicated elements is still a valid approach but takes a substantial organisational effort. A much more flexible and practical approach seems to be using existing TEI elements, and to add interpretations of them via semantic web references to the VID. This is making use of the best of both worlds: text encoding for scholarly editing and semantic web for shared ontologies.

Acknowledgements

We would like to thank Sean Winslow for his efforts in making our English readable.

Bibliography

- Álvarez Carbajal, Francisco Javier (2015). Towards a TEI model for the encoding of charters: developing an ODD for the medieval documents of the County of Luna. *TEI Conference*, Lyon 2015. Available from: <<http://tei2015.humanum.fr/en/papers/#acc-2>>
- Ansani, Michele (1999). Diplomatica (e diplomatisti) nell'arena digitale. *Scrineum Rivista* 1: 175–196.
- Ansani, Michele (2000-2020). *Codice Diplomatico della Lombardia Medievale*, Pavia: Università di Pavia. Available from: www.lombardiabeniculturali.it/cdlm (*Documentazione tecnica*: <http://www.lombardiabeniculturali.it/cdlm/progetto/documentazione>)
- Ansani, Michele. 2006. „Edizione digitale di fonti diplomatiche: esperienze, modelli testuali, priorità“. *Reti medievali* 7. DOI: [10.6092/1593-2214/140](https://doi.org/10.6092/1593-2214/140).
- Barbiche, Bernard. (1995). Rev. of “Vocabulaire internationale de la Diplomatique”. *BECh* 153,1: 207-208.
- Tim Berners-Lee, James Hendler, und Ora Lassila. (2001). „The Semantic Web. A new form of Web content that is meaningful to computers will unleash a revolution of new possibilities“. *Scientific American* 284/5: 34–43.
- Bradley, John, Dauvit Broun, Alice Rio, und Matthew Hammond (2019). „Exploring a Model for the Semantics of Medieval Legal Charters“. *International Journal of Humanities and Arts Computing* 13, Nr. 1–2 (10. Juni 2019) 136–154. DOI: [10.3366/ijhac.2017.0184](https://doi.org/10.3366/ijhac.2017.0184).
- Bubalo, Đorđe (2014). *Pragmatic Literacy in Medieval Serbia*, Utrecht Studies in Medieval Literacy 29, Turnhout 2014.
- CEMA: *Cartae Europae Medii Aevi*, ed. by Nicolas Perreaux (2021-) <https://lamop.pantheonsorbonne.fr/axes-recherche/livres-textes-langages/cema>
- Demonty, Philippe, ed. (1997). *Thesaurus Diplomaticus*. Turnhout: Brépols.
- Desenclos, Camille and Jolivet, Vincent (2014). Diple, Propositions Pour La Convergence de Schémas XML/TEI Dédiés à l'édition de Sources Diplomatiques. In: Ambrosio, A., Barret, S., and Vogeler, G., eds., *Digital Diplomatics. The Computer as a Tool for the Diplomatist?* Köln, Böhlau Verlag: 23-30. DOI: [10.7788/boehlau.9783412217020.23](https://doi.org/10.7788/boehlau.9783412217020.23).

- Dölger, Franz (1961). Die byzantinische und die mittelalterliche serbische Herrscherkanzlei, *XI^e Congrès international des Études Byzantines, Rapports IV*: 83–103.
- Dölger, Franz--Karayannopoulos, Johannes (1968). *Byzantinische Urkundenlehre I*, München 1968.
- Fekete, Lajos (1926). *Einführung in die osmanisch-türkische Diplomatie der türkischen Botmäßigkeit in Ungarn*, Budapest (Magyar Országos Levéltár kiadványai).
- Fostikov, Aleksandra (2017). Фостиков, Александра, Повеља цара Душана о поклону Ливаде и Палиокометице Хиландару (Хил. 34), *Стари српски архив* 16: 29-56 [Old Serbian archives; summary: The charter of Emperor Stefan Dušan about the gift of Livada and Paliokometica to the monastery of Hilandar (Hil. 34)]
- Gervers, Michael (1978). „Medieval Charters and the Computer: An Analysis Using Mark IV“. *Computers and the Humanities* 12 (1/2): 127–136.
- Große, Rolf (1996). Rev. of “Vocabulaire internationale de la Diplomatie”. *Francia* 23,1: 236-237.
- Guyotjeannin, Olivier (1996). Rev. of “Vocabulaire internationale de la Diplomatie”. *Revue Historique* 296,2: 431-432 <<http://www.jstor.org/stable/40956036>> / <<http://gallica.bnf.fr/ark:/12148/bpt6k56210202/f193.image>>
- Isaac, Antoine, Ed Summers (eds.) (2009). „SKOS Simple Knowledge Organization System Primer“. W3C Working Group notes. <https://www.w3.org/TR/2009/NOTE-skos-primer-20090818/>.
- Isasi Martínez, Carmen Ana Lobo Puga, Leyre Martín Aizpuru, Santiago Pérez Isasi, Elena Pierazzo y Paul Spence (2014): Guía para editar textos CHARTA según el estándar TEI: una propuesta. <<http://m.redcharta.es/investigacion/>>
- Ivanovs, Aleksandrs, and Varfolomeyev, Aleksey (2014). Some Approaches to the Semantic Publication of Charter Corpora. The Case of the Diplomatic Edition of Old Russian Charters. In: Ambrosio, A., Barret, S., and Vogeler, G., eds., *Digital Diplomatics. The Computer as a Tool for the Diplomatist?* Köln, Böhlau Verlag: 149–168.
- Ivanovs, Aleksandrs and Varfolomeyev, Aleksey (2017). “Service-Oriented Architecture of Intelligent Environment for Historical Records Studies”. *Procedia Computer Science* 104: 57–64. [10.1016/j.procs.2017.01.062](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.procs.2017.01.062).
- Karayannopoulos, Johannes (1998). Zu den “διά-Vermerken” der byzantinischen Kaiserurkunden, *Documenti medievali greci e latini*, eds. De Gregorio, E., Kresten, O., Spoleto: 203–232.

- Koch, Walter (2018). Die gefälschten österreichischen Hausprivilegien. In: Just, T., Kininger, K., Sommerlechner, A., and Weigl, H., eds., *Privilegium maius. Autopsie, Kontext und Karriere der Fälschungen Rudolfs IV. von Österreich*. Wien-Köln-Weimar: 77–90.
- Kölzer, Theo (2010). Diplomatics. In: *Handbook of medieval studies*: 405–424.
- Kuczera, Andreas (2020). „Regestenmodellierung im Graphen“. In *Graphentechnologien in den digitalen Geisteswissenschaften : Modellierung – Import – Analyse*.
https://kuczera.github.io/Graphentechnologien/20_Regestenmodellierung-im-Graphen.html.
- Kuczera, Andreas (2016). „Graphbasierte digitale Editionen“. Billet. *Mittelalter: Opuscula* (blog). 19. August 2016. <https://mittelalter.hypotheses.org/7994>.
- Lascaris, Michel (1931). Influences byzantines dans la diplomatie bulgare, serbe et slavo-roumaine, *Byzantinoslavica* 3: 500-510.
- LexMA. Lexikon des Mittelalters I-X, eds. Bautier, Robert-Henri et al, München/Zürich 1980-1999.
- Magnani, Eliana, and Nicolas Perreaux (2020), “A Medieval Epigraphic Corpus and Its Retro-Developments (CIFM-CBMA). The Exploratory Research of the COSME2 Consortium”, *Digital Scholarship in the Humanities, Special Issue proceedings of DH2019 conference*, DOI: [10.1093/llc/fqaa069](https://doi.org/10.1093/llc/fqaa069)
- Maksimovic, Ljubomir (1999). Das Kanzleiwesen der serbischen Herrscher, hgg. Hannick, Christian, *Kanzleiwesen und Kanzleisprachen im östlichen Europa*, AfD Beiheft 6: 25-53.
- Merowinger 2* (2001). *Die Urkunden der Merowinger*, hgg. von Kölzer, Theo, Monumenta Germaniae Historica, Hannover 2001.
- Miklosich, Franz (1858). *Monumenta Serbica spectantia historiam Serbiae, Bosnae, Ragusii*, Wien 1858.
- Misic, Sinisa--Koprivica, Marija (2015). Мишић, Синиша--Копривица, Марија, Општа хрисовуља цара Стефана Душана Хиландару, *Стари српски архив* 14: 65-106 [Old Serbian archives; summary: General chrysobull of tsar Stefan Dušan to Hilandar monastery]
- Mladenovic, Aleksandar (2007). Младеновић, Александар, *Повеље и писма деспота Стефана*, Београд 2007 [*Povelje i pisma despota Stefana*, Beograd]
- Monasterium.net, ed. by ICARus, Wien, 2005-2025 <<https://www.monasterium.net>>

- Nelson, Janet L., Burghart, A., Ciula, A., Garces, J., Spence, P., and Au, Z. (2005-2018). *ASChart. Anglo-Saxon Charters*. Available from: <http://www.aschart.kcl.ac.uk/index.html>
- Oikonomidès, Nicolas (1985). La chancellerie impériale de Byzance du 13e au 15e siècle, *Revue des études byzantines* 43: 167-195.
- Oxford handbook of Byzantine studies (2008). *The Oxford Handbook of Byzantine Studies*, eds. Jeffreys, E., Haldon, J., Cormack, R., New York, 2008.
- Perreaux, Nicolas (27.5.2020), “Cartae Europae Medii Aevi. Méthodes, Enjeux et Possibilités d’un Corpus Diplomatique Européen” (YouTube) <<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=7tkWQghT1zQ>> [accessed 18 Januar 2025]
- Porcic, Nebojsa (2015). The Menologem in Serbian Medieval Document-Making, eds. Miljkovic, Bojan and Dzelebdzic, Dejan, *Perivolos I*, Beograd: 285–298.
- Porcic, Nebojsa (2016). Порчић, Небојша, “Царске шаре црвене”: о заступљености и обрасцима употребе црвеног мастила у документима Немањића, *Зборник радова Византолошког института* 53: 255-273 [*Zbornik radova Vizantološkog instituta*; summary: “Lines of royal red”: on the presence and patterns of use of red ink in Nemanjid documents]
- Porcic, Nebojsa--Isailovic, Neven (2019). Порчић, Небојша--Исаиловић, Невен, Документи средњовековних владара Србије и Босне у венецијанским збиркама, Београд 2019 [summary: Documents of Rulers of Medieval Serbia and Bosnia in Venetian Collections]
- Poulimenou, S., Asonitis, S. and Poulos, M. (2009). Metadata Encoding for the Documents based on the Rules of Diplomatics Science. In: Sicilas, A. and Lytras, M.D., eds. *Metadata and Semantics, Proceedings of the 2th International Conference on Metadata and Semantics Research 11-12 October 2007*. Berlin 2009: 91-100.
- Reychmann, Jan, and & Zajaczkowski, Ananiasz (1968). *Handbook of Ottoman-Turkish Diplomatics*, rev. and exp. transl. by Andrew S. Ehrenkreutz, Mouton et al. (Publications in Near and Middle East Studies--Columbia University)
- Sahle, Patrick (2013). *Digitale Editionsformen. Zum Umgang mit der Überlieferung unter den Bedingungen des Medienwandels*. Schriften des Instituts für Dokumentologie und Editorik. 3 vols. Norderstedt (Schriften des Instituts für Dokumentologie und Editorik 7-9).
- Sahle, Patrick (2016). „What Is a Scholarly Digital Edition?“ In *Digital Scholarly Editing: Theories and Practices*, herausgegeben von Matthew James Driscoll und Elena Pierazzo. Cambridge (Digital Humanities Series 4): 19–40 [DOI: 10.11647/OBP.0095.02](https://doi.org/10.11647/OBP.0095.02).

- Schuh, Dieter (1978). Ergebnisse und Aspekte tibetischer Urkundenforschung, In: Ligeti, Louis, ed. *Proceedings of the Csoma de Kőrös Memorial Symposium*, hg. v. Louis Ligeti, Budapest.
- Sipl, Colin--Burghardt, Manuel (2023). Modelling Entity Relations in Charter Regests of the St. Katharinenhospital in Regensburg with CIDOC-CRM Ontology, eds. Vujosevic, Zarko and Porcic, Nebojsa, *Archives and Archival Research in the Digital Environment*, Belgrade 2023: 171–184.
- Spence, Paul. (2014). Siete retos en edición digital para las fuentes documentales. *Scriptum Digital* 3: 153-181.
- TEI Consortium (2020). att.global.rendition. In: TEI Consortium *P5: Guidelines for Electronic Text Encoding and Interchange*, available from: <https://tei-c.org/release/doc/tei-p5-doc/en/html/ref-att.global.rendition.html>
- Vocabulaire International de la Diplomatie* (1997) ed. Carcél Ortí 1997 (1. ed. 1994)
- Vogeler, Georg (2004). Ein Standard für die Digitalisierung mittelalterlicher Urkunden mit XML. Bericht von einem internationalen Workshop in München 5./6. April 2004. AfD 50: 23–34.
- Vogeler, Georg (2005) 'Towards a Standard of Encoding Medieval Charters with XML', *Literary and Linguistic Computing*, 20(3): 269–280. doi: [10.1093/lc/fqi031](https://doi.org/10.1093/lc/fqi031).
- Vogeler, Georg (2006) 'Charters Encoding Initiative (CEI) : Zu Möglichkeiten der Integration mit Hilfe eines Standards für Urkundendigitalisierung', in *Alte Archive-- Neue Technologien*, hg. v. Thomas Aigner und Karin Winter. St. Pölten: 181–198.
- Vogeler, Georg (2010) 'Charters Encoding Initiative Overview', *Digital Proceedings of the Lawrence J. Schoenberg Symposium on Manuscript Studies in the Digital Age*, 2(1), article 8. <https://repository.upenn.edu/ljsproceedings/vol2/iss1/8/>
- Vogeler, Georg (2013). Von der Terminologie zur Ontologie. Das 'Vocabulaire international de la diplomatie' als Ressource des Semantic Web. *Francia* 40: 281–297.
- Vogeler, Georg (2015). „Die Text Encoding Initiative (TEI) als Werkzeug des Urkundeneditors--Erfahrungen und Desiderate“. In *Papsturkundenforschung zwischen internationaler Vernetzung und Digitalisierung. Neue Zugangsweisen zur europäischen Schriftgeschichte*, hg. v. Irmgard Fees, Benedikt Hotz, u. Benjamin Schönfeld. res doctae. Göttingen. https://rep.adw-goe.de/bitstream/handle/11858/00-001S-0000-0023-9A13-A/6_Vogeler.pdf.
- Vogeler, Georg (2018). Digital Diplomatics: The Evolution of a European Tradition or a Generic Concept?. In: Cubelic, S., Zotter, A. and Michaels, A., eds. *Studies in*

Historical Documents from Nepal and India. Documenta Nepalica: 85-109. DOI: [10.17885/heiup.331.454](https://doi.org/10.17885/heiup.331.454)

Vogeler, Georg (2019). Versioning Charters: On the Multiple Identities of Historical Legal Documents and their Digital Representation. In *Bleier, Roman and Winslow, Sean M., eds. Versioning Cultural Objects*, Schriften des Instituts für Dokumentologie und Editorik 13. Norderstedt: 127–50.

Vujosevic, Zarko (2005). Вујошевић, Жарко, Повеља краља Стефана Душана о цркви Светог Николе у Добрушти, *Стари српски архив* 4: 51-67 [*Anciennes archives serbes*; abstract: Charte du roi Stefan Dušan concernant l'église Saint-Nicolas à Dobrušta]

Vujosevic, Zarko, Porcic, Nebojsa and Zivojinovic, Dragic M. (2014). Das serbische Kanzleiwesen. Die Herausforderung der digitalen Diplomatie. In: Ambrosio, A., Barret, S., and Vogeler, G., eds., *Digital Diplomats. The Computer as a Tool for the Diplomatist?* Köln, Böhlau Verlag: 133–147.

Vujosevic, Zarko--Old Wine (2019). Old Wine into New Skins: The Charters Database *Diplomatarium Serbicum Digitale*. In: Popovic, M., Polloczek, W., Koschicek, B. and Eichert, S. *Power in Landscape. Geographic and Digital Approaches on Historical Research*. Leipzig, Eudora-Verlag: 215–225.

Vujosevic, Zarko--Clergy (2019). On the Role of the Clergy in the Composition of Serbian Medieval Royal Charters, *Initial. A Review of Medieval Studies* 7: 73-82.

Vujosevic, Zarko--AfD (2020). Das Phänomen Herrscherkanzlei im mittelalterlichen Serbien, *AfD* 66: 239-276.

Vujosevic, Zarko--Cetinje, Stefan (2020). Cetinje: Die Urkunden der Herrscher von Serbien und Zeta in den Sammlungen von Cetinje (1212?-1495), 1212-99-99 F Stefan Nemanjic, in: *monasterium.net*, URL: <https://www.monasterium.net/mom/ca0f8ea7-3cc6-48cc-8f8e-a73cc618cc34/2b9741e8-01b8-459c-9741-e801b8d59c29/charter>

Vujosevic, Zarko--Cetinje, Milutin (2020). Cetinje: Die Urkunden der Herrscher von Serbien und Zeta in den Sammlungen von Cetinje (1212?-1495) 1314-02-99 tpq Milutin, in: *monasterium.net*, URL: <https://www.monasterium.net/mom/ca0f8ea7-3cc6-48cc-8f8e-a73cc618cc34/b1e36b5c-d463-407a-a36b-5cd463507a6b/charter>

Winslow, Sean (2018): "Modelling Authentication", *TEI2018*, Tokyo

Winslow, Sean (2019). "Modelling charters in TEI P5: the TEI_CEI ODD". *TEI 2019 Book of Abstracts*. <<https://gams.uni-graz.at/o:tei2019.132/sdef:TEI/get?context=context:tei2019.panels>>

Winslow, Sean M. (2020–2022) "Authenticating Features in the TEI". *Journal of the Text Encoding Initiative* 13: 1–21.